

“Probing galaxy interaction mechanisms in merging clusters with HI”

based on a recent paper by
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+19°45'

+40'

+35'

11^h39^m45^s

39^m30^s

39^m15^s

39^m00^s

38^m45^s

HI in
FGC1287
group

Content

- Interactions and impact on HI content and resolved morphology
- Abell 1367: a merging cluster
- Alternative HI perturbation measurements
- Summary

HI PERTURBATION

- HI in isolated galaxies, interacting pairs, groups and cluster galaxies shows HI morphology and kinematics to be highly sensitive to interactions. (Scott et al. 2010, 2012, 2014, 2015, submitted, Sengupta et al. 2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, Martinez-Delgado et al. 2009).
- At the extreme, a pair interaction can temporarily displace $\sim 50\%$ ($9.5 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$) of the pair's HI well outside the edges of optical disks (Sengupta 2013).
- Figures: white and green contours = HI

HI Perturbations - clusters

- HI, especially that at the disk edges of LTGs is sensitive to environmental effects, through a wide range of mechanisms, e.g.,
 - ram pressure stripping of HI from LTGs infalling into clusters
 - tidal HI stripping, two types for LTGs infalling to clusters:
 1. “harassment” (repeated low impact, high velocity)
 2. pre-processing (within infalling groups, high impact, low velocity)

Cluster LTG's HI Deficiency

- HI Deficiency (Def HI) is defined as:
 $\log(\text{H}_{\text{expected}}/\text{H}_{\text{observed}})$
+ = deficient, - = excess
(Haynes & Giovanelli 1984)
- Fraction of HI deficient late type galaxies (LTGs) increases with proximity to cluster centres (Solanes et al. 2001)
- HI deficiency correlated with truncated $H\alpha$ (SF) and dust disks (Koopmann & Kenney 2004; Cortese et al. 2012)

HI in clusters

- Evidence cluster environment is impacting optical properties of late type galaxies (LTGs), out to several Abell radii (Ellingson 2004)
- ISM stripping from LTGs is an important aspect of transformation of LTGs to earlier Hubble types
- Low z clusters - consensus ram pressure stripping is the dominant LTG transforming mechanism (Boselli et al. 2016)
- It is unclear the extent to which ram pressure and/or tidal mechanisms operate at different radii or clusters of different types, or as a function of z

Abell 1367

- ($z = 0.02$) merging cluster: X-ray emission (cyan contours) from the ICM (NW and SE sub-cluster)
- A 1367 central ICM density $\sim 1/5$ of Coma (Fukazawa et al 2004).

A1367: ISM stripping observations

- HI single dish $1^\circ \times 5^\circ$ blind survey (AGES n=43)
- HI interferometric resolved (VLA n=30)
- H α deep imaging (Yagi et al. 2017). H α tails longer, more massive and more frequent in A1367 compared to Coma
- There are examples of multiple mechanisms operating simultaneously, e.g., tidally loosened of gas aiding ram pressure stripping

Pair interaction

Preprocessing + ram pressure

HI contours on H alpha
Scott et al. 2017 (subm.)

Harassment + ram pressure?

Scott et al. 2015

A Question

- In A1367, unlike Coma, HI deficiencies do not show a clear trend with cluster centric distance (Scott et al. 2010)
- Determining Def HI uncertain and spatially resolved mapping HI is expensive
- Can HI be used to determine the dominant mechanism perturbing LTG ISM in A1367 and other clusters?
- Explore this question: investigate 4 HI perturbations signatures:
 - HI profile asymmetry, A_{flux}
 - opt – HI velocity or position offset

Scott et al 2010

Four HI perturbation signatures

Available HI single dish (AGES) and interferometric resolved (VLA) data for A 1367 was used to investigate four types HI perturbation signatures:

1 Asymmetries in the HI (AGES) profiles A_{flux}

A_{flux} ratio is a measure of the asymmetry in its integrated HI flux (within its W_{20} velocity range) at velocities above and below a galaxy's systemic velocity, V_{HI} (Espada et al. 2011)

Histogram: A1367 A_{flux}

26% A1367 (AGES) have $A_{flux} > 3\sigma$ in an isolated sample (2%) and other dense environments (10 to 20%)

Four HI perturbation signatures

1 Asymmetries in the HI profile A_{flux}

Two statistically significant relations for LTGs with $A_{\text{flux}} > 1.26$ in isolated sample found:

- Subcluster distance ($r = -0.598$)
- HI deficiency ($r = 0.522$)

56% of LTGs with $A_{\text{flux}} > 1.26$ are members of groups and pairs => significant contribution from tidal interactions

Symbols:

Black $A_{\text{flux}} > 2 \sigma$ ($A_{\text{flux}} = 1.26$) in isolated sample

Red $A_{\text{flux}} < 2 \sigma$ ($A_{\text{flux}} = 1.26$) in isolated sample

Open symbols = members of groups and pairs

Four HI perturbation signatures

2 Differences between optical and HI velocities

Velocity offsets were found in a few cases, where A_{flux} is also high and tidal interactions are suspected

3 Offsets between single dish HI and optical positions (AGES HI offsets)

Single dish HI offsets orientation and projected magnitude x 20

Surprisingly the largest offsets ($> 3\sigma$ pointing uncertainties) are not near the cluster centre. One case is group tidal interaction and another is triplet

FGC 1287 raises the question of the effectiveness of ram pressure stripping beyond the virial radius and X-ray detected ICM

Four HI perturbation signatures

4 Offsets between intensity maxima in resolved HI maps and optical positions (Resolved HI VLA offsets)

- Magnitude of A1367 resolved offsets are not distinguishable from those in THINGS maps (proxy for isolated galaxies) smoothed to similar resolution
- Location of HI maximum column density in resolved maps depends on resolution
- At lower resolutions the HI maximum moves toward HI flux weighted mean position, i.e., the Single Dish HI position

Conclusion: unresolved offset reflects large scale displacement of low density gas

VLA HI image of NGC2976 ($D = 3.56$ Mpc) from THINGS. $+ =$
location of resolved maxima for 15" (purple), 60" (cyan), 90" (green)
120" (red) and 240" (white) beams. The circles of the same colour
indicate the FWHP beam. The yellow marks the optical centre

A1367: HI perturbation signatures

- LTGs with HI AGES HI detections
- LTGs with AGES $A_{\text{flux}} > 2\sigma$
- Subcluster positions (NW and SE)
- ↗ AGES HI offset x 20

Neither HI AGES offsets
> 2σ nor $A_{\text{flux}} > 2\sigma$
are well correlated with
galaxy density or ICM,
traced by X-ray emission

Summary

- Extensive HI data for Abell 1367 reveal widespread strong ongoing HI interaction signatures, within and beyond the virial radius. Almost all LTGs with HI detections show at least one HI perturbation signature
- The projected distribution of the A_{flux} and the single dish offsets (most relevant HI perturbation signatures) are not easily interpreted
- The $A_{\text{flux}} (> 2\sigma)$ indicator correlates with HI def and sub-cluster centric distance, implying a connection with galaxies undergoing recent interactions
- 56% of LTGs with $A_{\text{flux}} (> 2\sigma)$ are group or pair members suggesting a connection to tidal interactions
- Detailed studies have found cases where multiple mechanisms appear to operate simultaneously

The End